

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
**EDUCATION AND
TECHNOLOGY (AJET)**

ISSN: 2832-9481 (ONLINE)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 1 (2022)

Indexed in

PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

TikTok Consumption and Level of Class Engagement of Performing Arts Students in the New Normal: Destructive or Beneficial?

Joseph Lobo^{1*}, Genesis Dimalanta², Clarenz Bautista³, Edison Buan¹, Don Al De Dios³

Article Information

Received: June 03, 2022

Accepted: June 09, 2022

Published: June 12, 2022

Keywords

*Engagement, Local College,
Performing Arts students, TikTok*

ABSTRACT

TikTok has been widely used by Filipino youths, most especially students, for entertainment purposes in between or after class as pass time activity. Previous studies were already conducted in regards to the positive and negative effect of using TikTok to students' academic performance. This present study aims to determine if TikTok can predict the level of engagement of students. 103 college students currently enrolled under the Bachelor of Performing Arts at City College of Angeles participated in this study. Independent T-test analysis was performed to examine the difference between gender in terms of TikTok consumption and level of engagement; Pearson correlation coefficient analysis was also used to determine the relationship between TikTok consumption and level of engagement; lastly, Linear regression was utilized to predict the relationship of TikTok consumption to the level of engagement of students. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference between TikTok consumption and level of engagement in terms of gender. Moreover, a significant relationship was observed between TikTok consumption and level of engagement. Finally, TikTok consumption positively predicts the level of engagement of students. In line with this, recommendations were proposed based on the results of this study. This present study offers new standpoint in the smart and responsible use of TikTok application and how it can positively affect the level of engagement of students in a local college setting.

INTRODUCTION

In this post-pandemic time, most of the educational institutions in the Philippines have started implementing a limited face-to-face class from the basic education to the tertiary level. However, in the current situation of City College of Angeles, students are still in the online class setting due to college's infrastructure development and it is being used by the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Angeles as vaccination center. Most of the students are staying home and still enters their respective classes through online educational platforms. Due to loads of coursework that they need to fulfill, students mostly rely on TikTok as one of their pass time activities, aside from other social networking applications. In this present study, this aims to understand the relationship between the use of TikTok to the level of engagement of the students. Due to rampant consumption of students on the said application, this present study would also like to further determine if the use of the said application may positively or negatively affect the engagement of the students on their online class. In order to examine the effect of the said application to students' engagement, further investigation should be performed. This present study will provide insights that will help both professors and students on how TikTok may affect engagement of students and how it should be addressed based on the findings that this present study will obtain.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The TikTok Application and Class Engagement

TikTok (formerly known as Music.ly) was founded by Zhang Yiming in September 2016 (Montag et al., 2021a).

In a just short span of time, this application has been one of the successful apps from Chinese origin in terms of global distribution. Most especially in Angeles City, Philippines, this application has been widely used by various generation. It has become an increasingly popular app for people of many different ages to use (Mekler, 2021b). Added by Mekler, this application allow users can create their own videos they want on this application and post it for anyone to see as well as for entertainment purposes. In this, the said application has attracted a lot of people most especially college students. This application has been considered as the holy grail of students – aside from other social media applications – most students use this application as their recreational activity after their online class and finishing tons of course work.

The involvement of students is one of the determinants of academic success (Chiu, 2022; Sneck et al., 2022). Student engagement, in general, refers to the active participation in a variety of academic and co-curricular, as well as commitment to achieving learning objectives (Ginting, 2021). Students who are highly engaged academically are more likely to devote their time and effort to achieve their goals. This also refers to the effort of the learner to promote his or her psychological commitment, or invest (McKee & Ntokos, 2022), to stay engaged in the learning process to acquire knowledge and build critical thinking (Rajabalee et al., 2020; Reinke, 2019). Added by Rajabalee et. al., this is also associated with the learner's feeling of personal motivation in the subject or course, which keeps the learner active in order to interact with the course contents, professors and classmates respectively.

Relationship between TikTok consumption and

¹ Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences, City College of Angeles, Philippines

² Institute of Arts, Sciences and Teacher Education, Mabalacat City College, Philippines.

³ Physical Education, Recreation and Sports Department, Pampanga State Agricultural University, Philippines.

* Corresponding author's e-mail: jtoledolobo@gmail.com

level of class engagement

There are already previous studies that were conducted regarding the positive and negative impact of the use of TikTok application to the academic performance of students since the start of the pandemic (De Guzman Jr., n.d.; Hayes et al., 2020; Kaur, 2020; Mekler, 2021a; Montag et al., 2021; Putu et al., 2022; Vhatkar, A., & Mali, 2021) which are highly supported with strong theoretical and conceptual underpinnings and robust findings. Previous studies have also shown the possible application and implementation of TikTok as an education tool which may lead to academic success of students (Ismail et al., 2021; Putri, 2021; Sajonia, 2022). However, there are only few previously conducted studies which focuses on the relationship of TikTok – its positive and negative effect – to one of the determinants of academic success which is the engagement of students, most especially in a local setting, meaning further investigation should be performed. In this, this current study aims to determine TikTok application’s effect to the class engagement of students.

METHODS

Design

This study is a quantitative in design which aims to describe the level of TikTok consumption and class engagement of students. It also aims to determine if there is a significant difference in the application consumption and class engagement of students based on gender. Additionally, it also seeks if both TikTok consumption and class engagement are correlated to each other. Lastly, this study would also like to further determine if TikTok can predict the class engagement of the students.

Population and Sampling

The target respondents of the study are students who are currently enrolled in Bachelor of Performing Arts (BPeA) program this Academic Year 2021-2022 under the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences at City College of Angeles, Pampanga, Philippines. This study has utilized Judgment Sampling to gather participants for the study. Also called as purposive sampling, a sampling technique where the researcher deliberately chooses participants for the study due to the qualities the participants possess (Etikan, 2016).

Instrumentation

There are two instruments that were utilized on this study. The first questionnaire was adapted from De Guzman Jr. (n.d.). From the original eight scenarios stated in the questionnaire, the researcher has only used one out of the eight scenarios to be fitted for the study. It is a 24-item questionnaire which describes the extent of Social Networking Sites (SNS) consumption of the students. Also, the researcher replaced some words such as “SNS” to “TikTok” to tailor fit and align it to the main purpose of the study. The responses of the students will then be recorded on a 4-point Likert scale from 1 ‘strongly disagree’ to 4 ‘strongly agree.’

The second questionnaire was adopted from Handelsman

et al. (2010) which is the Student Engagement Questionnaire (SEQ). It is a 23-item questionnaire which describes the level of class engagement of students. Responses of the students are then recorded on a 4-point Likert scale from 1 ‘not at all characteristic of me’ to 4 ‘very characteristic of me.’

Data Gathering

Gathering of data was made possible by the approval from the Dean of the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences. The questionnaire was floated via online survey through Google Form. The said online questionnaire can be filled-out by the students within 5-10 minutes. All gathered data from the Google Form was then be exported into an excel file to be used for data analysis. After the data gathered were used for the analysis, the excel file was encrypted with a password where the researchers has only the personal access to it.

Data Analysis

Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Test (*a or coefficient alpha*) was used to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaires to be used for the study. It is a measure of internal consistency, i.e., how closely related a set of items are as a group (Sileyew, 2019). It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. From the pilot testing that was made to non-BPeA students (N=50), Table 1 illustrates the reliability test of both SNS Scale and SEQ which resulted to a Cronbach’s Alpha value of .897 and .947 which are both very reliable. In this, both of the questionnaires can be used for the conduct of the study. grounded on Sigmund Freud psychoanalysis theory of development focusing more on the development of the ego, the part of the personality which is partly conscious and partly unconscious which carried our identity and the sense of self which says who we are (Widick et al.,1978).

Table 1: Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Test for Social Network Sites (SNS) Utilization Scale and Student Engagement Questionnaire (SEQ)

Questionnaire	Cronbach’s Alpha	N of items	Level of Reliability
Social Network Sites Utilizations (SNS) Scale	.897	24	Very Reliable
Student Engagement Questionnaire (SEQ)	.941	23	Very Reliable

In order to recognize the appropriate statistical test to be used in the research study, normality test was conducted. Table 2 revealed that results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk. It was shown that the p-value of TikTok consumption and level of engagement for both male and female are higher than .05 (>.05); as a result, the data are considered normally distributed. In this, a parametric test is appropriate for this study.

Frequency (f) and **Percentage (%)** were used to describe the number of students who have answered the survey based on gender. **Mean (M)** and **Standard Deviation (SD)** were also utilized to describe the level of TikTok

Table 2: Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality

	Gender	df	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		Shapiro-Wilk	
			Statistics	p-value	Statistics	p-value
TikTok Consumption	Male	41	.101	.200*	.949	.064
	Female	62	.090	.200*	.945	.008
Level of Engagement	Male	41	.124	.114	.948	.057
	Female	62	.104	.096	.962	.055

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

consumption and level of class engagement of students. In order to interpret the results on the level of application consumption and engagement of students, the researcher have employed a point-scale interpretation based on the average weighted mean of each statement which is shown in Table 3.

Independent Samples T-test was also applied to determine the significant difference between TikTok consumption and engagement by gender. A parametric test which tells whether there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores for the two groups or not (Gerald,

2018). Pearson Correlation Coefficient was also used to determine the relationship between TikTok consumption and level of engagement of students. This is a measure of an association between variables (Schober & Schwarte, 2018). Lastly, Linear Regression was operated to predict the relationship of TikTok consumption to the level of engagement of students. A modeling technique where a dependent variable is predicted based on one independent variable (Kraemer & Blasey, 2016).

In this regard, the following are the formulated hypotheses that were tested on this study according to statistical analysis used for each data shown in Table 4:

Table 3: Descriptive interpretation on the level of TikTok Consumption and Level of Engagement

Range of Weighted Mean	Interpretation
3.26 – 4.00	Very High
2.51 – 3.25	High
1.76 – 2.50	Low
1.00 – 1.75	Very Low

Table 4.1: Hypotheses of the Study

Hypotheses	Variables	Statistical Analysis
H1 There is no significant difference between gender and TikTok consumption	Gender and TC	Independent Samples T-Test
H2 There is no significant difference between gender and level of class engagement.	Gender and CE	Independent Samples T-Test
H3 There is no significant relationship between TikTok consumption and level of class engagement.	TC and CE	Pearson Correlation Coefficient
H4 TikTok consumption does not predict the level of class engagement of BPeA students.	TC and CE	Linear Regression

*TC-TikTok Consumption; CE-Class Engagement

RESULTS

IBM SPSS 26 was used to run all the data gathered and to employ the statistical treatment to be used. The adapted questionnaires which were utilized for the study have been answered by 103 students currently enrolled in the Bachelor of Performing Arts (BPeA) program under the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences at City College of Angeles, Angeles City, Philippines

Table 4 illustrates the respondents’ demographic profile based on gender. The results yielded that most of the respondents are female (N=62), which is 60.2% from the total sample size, while male (N=41) is 39.8%.

Table 5 illustrates the level of TikTok consumption of BPeA students. The highlighted statements (corresponds to ‘very high’) which all garnered the highest mean among the respondents are: my academics are my main focus (M= 3.39, SD = .660); I only use SNS/Tiktok when I

Table 4.2: Demographic Profile of Students by Gender

Gender	f	%
Male	41	39.8
Female	62	60.2
Total n and %	103	100

Table 5: Level of TikTok Consumption of Students

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I use my SNS/Tiktok account for school work.	2.46	.861	L
I use my SNS/Tiktok account to communicate with my classmates.	2.28	.772	L
I use my SNS/Tiktok to communicate for group projects.	2.29	.775	L
I use my SNS/Tiktok as a break while studying.	2.95	.856	H
I use my SNS/Tiktok as a free time activity.	3.27	.795	VH
I use my SNS/Tiktok to procrastinate when I should be studying.	2.25	.750	L
I use my SNS/Tiktok to procrastinate if I am struggling.	2.57	.881	H
SNS/Tiktok is time consuming.	2.85	.821	H
SNS/Tiktok is an academic distraction.	2.40	.856	L
SNS/Tiktok decrease my academic performance.	2.28	.845	L
SNS/Tiktok take time away from studying.	2.39	.807	L
SNS/Tiktok distract me from studying.	2.23	.807	L
I multitask with my SNS/Tiktok while studying.	2.50	.839	L
I am a responsible person about school work.	3.25	.682	H
I am good at multitasking with SNS/Tiktok.	2.70	.850	H
No one on my SNS/Tiktok is worth me getting failing grades.	2.77	.807	H
I do not spend excessive amount of time on my SNS/Tiktok.	3.04	.740	H
I do not go on SNS/Tiktok during class.	3.02	.792	H
I check my SNS/Tiktok during class.	2.26	.766	L
I do not have SNS/Tiktok up while doing homework.	2.83	.793	H
I don't allow SNS/Tiktok to impact my academics.	3.09	.806	H
My academics are my main focus.	3.39	.660	VH
When I am doing my work for school; I do not check my SNS/Tiktok	3.03	.785	H
I only use SNS/Tiktok when I have the time for it.	3.33	.772	VH
Overall Mean	2.72	.421	H

*VL-Low; L-Low; H-High; VH-Very High

have the time for it (M = 3.33, SD = .772); and, I use my SNS/Tiktok as a break while studying (M = 3.27, SD = .795). Overall, the level of TikTok consumption of BPeA students was found out to be high (M = 2.72, SD = .421). Table 6 illustrates the level of class engagement of students. The results revealed that most of the statements that were asked to students garnered an interpretation of 'very high' and 'high' respectively. The highest

notable statements (corresponds to 'very high') which all garnered the highest mean among the statements from the respondents are coming to online class everyday (M = 3.51, SD = .558); putting fourth effort (M = 3.45, SD = .573); and, listening carefully to class (M = 3.45, SD = .555). In summary, the level of engagement of BPeA students was found out be very high (M = 3.29, SD = .430).

Table 6. Level of Class Engagement of Students

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Raising my hand in class	3.07	.820	H
Participating actively in small group discussions	3.34	.667	VH
Asking questions when I don't understand the instructor	3.14	.805	H
Doing all the homework problems	3.43	.587	VH
Coming to online class everyday	3.51	.558	VH
Going to the professor's office hours to review assignments or tests, or to ask questions	2.89	.839	H
Thinking about the course between class meetings	3.07	.690	H
Finding ways to make the course interesting to me	3.27	.662	VH
Taking good notes in class	3.18	.681	H

Looking over class notes between classes to make sure I understand the material	3.19	.728	H
Really desiring to learn the material	3.36	.559	VH
Being confident that I can learn and do well in the class	3.31	.627	VH
Putting forth effort	3.45	.573	VH
Being organized	3.43	.605	VH
Getting a good grade	3.40	.567	VH
Doing well on the tests	3.33	.584	VH
Staying up on the readings	3.18	.669	H
Having fun in class	3.37	.560	VH
Helping fellow students	3.37	.560	VH
Making sure to study on a regular basis	3.31	.578	VH
Finding ways to make the course material relevant to my life	3.43	.622	VH
Applying course material to my life	3.36	.624	VH
Listening carefully in class	3.45	.555	VH
Overall Mean	3.29	.430	VH

*VL-Low; L-Low; H-High; VH-Very High

Table 7 illustrates the result from the independent t-test analysis used between the level of TikTok consumption of the students being independent of gender of BPeA students. According to the Levene's test for equality of variances, the sig. value is .012 which is lower than $\alpha = .05$. This means, that the assumption of equal variance has not been violated, therefore interpreting the t-value provided in the equal variances assumed line. It was found out that there is no statistically significant difference between gender $t(60.2) = .410, p = .683$, even male ($M = 2.75, SD = .534$) has a higher TikTok consumption than female ($M = 2.71, SD = .330$).

Table 7: Independent T-test analysis on the level of TikTok consumption being independent of gender of BPeA students

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-test	Sig	Decision
Male	41	2.75	.534	60.2	.410	.683	Not Significant
Female	62	2.71	.330				

Table 8: Independent T-test analysis on the level of engagement being independent of gender of BPeA students

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-test	Sig	Decision
Male	41	3.35	.425	101	1.090	.277	Not Significant
Female	62	3.25	.432				

Table 9: Relationship between TikTok Consumption to Class Engagement

Correlations	
Engagement	
TikTok Consumption	r = .367, p < .001
N	103

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

relationship between TikTok consumption and class engagement of BPeA students by utilizing Pearson correlation coefficient. The results found out that TikTok consumption has a positive significant relationship to class engagement ($r = .367, p < .001$). The analysis revealed

Table 8 illustrates the result from the independent t-test analysis used between the level of engagement of the students being independent of gender of BPeA students. According to the Levene's test for equality of variances, the sig. value is .884 which is higher than $\alpha = .05$. This means, that the assumption of equal variance has been violated, therefore interpreting the t-test value provided in the equal variances not assumed line. The results found out that there is no statistically significant difference between gender, $t(101) = 1.090, p = .277$, even female ($M = 3.35, SD = .425$) has a higher level of engagement than male ($M = 3.25, SD = .432$). Table 9 illustrates the

that TikTok consumption has a significant positive relationship with engagement ($\beta = .374, p < .001$). TikTok consumption accounts for 13.4% for the variance in the level of engagement of the students $F(1, 102) = 15.691, p < .001$.

Table 10: Linear Regression analysis between TikTok consumption and engagement of BPeA students

Model Analysis									
					Change Statistics				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.367a	.134	.126	.40211	.134	15.691	1	101	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), TikTok Consumption

b. Dependent Variable: Engagement

Anova						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Regression	2.537	1	2.537	15.691	.000b	
Residual	16.331	101	.162			
Total	18.868	102				

a. Dependent Variable: Engagement

b. Predictors: (Constant), TikTok Consumption

Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	Mean Square	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	2.277	.261		8.734	.000	
TikTok	.374	.094	.367	3.961	.000	

a. Dependent Variable: Engagement

DISCUSSION

Level of TikTok Consumption and class engagement of students

In the analysis on the response of students regarding their consumption of TikTok, most of the statements that were interpreted as very high and high are those which particularly highlights their responsible and smart use of the said social networking application. Based on the analysis, it can be construed that students uses TikTok as a form of entertainment during their break or as a free time activity, and most of the respondents answered that TikTok should not be a hindrance on their academic performance. From the findings of Vhatkar & Mali (2021a), it was revealed that most of the students use TikTok is only used as pass time activity and for relaxation (Jayarathne, n.d.); and should not be a hindrance in their academic engagement and performance. During this pandemic, students cannot carry out activities in school outside their homes that is why TikTok is one of the entertainment chosen to everyday life (Putu et al., 2022) by the students.

Based on the analysis on the response of students regarding their level of engagement during online class, the results yielded that most of the BPeA students are participative, attentive, and highly engaged during their classes. This result is highly significant because even we are still in the midst of post-pandemic, students are still highly engaged on their studies even in an online class setting. Meaning, the more they are highly participative

and engaged in the teaching and learning process, it can result to exceedingly performing students.

Difference in TikTok consumption and level of engagement according to Gender

From the independent t-test that was utilized, the result found out that there is no statistically significant difference found between TikTok consumption and gender of students. On the other hand, from the comparison of means, it was found out that male has a higher consumption compare to female students. Opposite from the study findings of (Montag et al., 2021b), it was seen that female uses the platform more than males. However, the scope of Montag et. al. study is more focused on a global scale rather than a specific set of population. Result of this finding may be extended to other set of population to confirm if there is a difference in the consumption of the application between gender. Ergo, in this study, it can be construed that regardless of gender, both are equal in terms of consumption of the application.

It was also found out that there is no statistically significant difference between level of engagement and gender of students. Study of Nugroho et al. (2021) supported the finding of this study, wherein it was found out that there is no significant difference in the level of student engagement in terms of gender during COVID-19 Pandemic. Findings of Baloran et al. (2021) also revealed that there is no statistically significant difference in student engagement in terms of gender in online learning. Based

on the comparison of means, it was found out that males are highly engaged than female students. Contrary to the result of Korlat et al. (2021), where females are more highly engaged than male students on their online class during this pandemic. Hartono et al. (2019) also found out that the score of female engagement is higher than male students on their history subject. Overall, based on the t-test analysis, it can be stated that regardless of gender, all BPeA students are highly engaged to their online classes.

Relationship between TikTok consumption and its effect to the level of engagement of students

The relationship between TikTok consumption and level of engagement of students was found out to be significantly related based on the Pearson correlation coefficient analysis. The findings of this study can be supported by Salasac & Lobo (2022) that confirms the relationship between the two variables. In the linear regression analysis utilized to determine the effect of TikTok consumption to students’ engagement, the results yielded that TikTok consumption has a significant positive relationship with engagement. It can be construed that TikTok consumption has a positive effect to students’ engagement. Supported by the study findings of Nepali (2021) revealed that 90% of the respondents have positively retorted that social media (e.g., TikTok) helped them on their academic performance; a result from highly engaged students. The claim of this study can also be supported by the study of Hayes et al. (2020), where the findings revealed that TikTok can be used to enhance undergraduate engagement. On contrary, based on the findings of Mekler (2021c), it was found out that the more college students spent on TikTok each day, the more they become distracted when they are trying to pay attention in class and complete course works. In this, TikTok can impact college students’ abilities to be able to pay attention in class and get their schoolwork done or may have the possibility of doing worse in class if they have and use the app TikTok, added by Mekler. The same result was discovered by Vhatkar & Mali (2021b), that the said application has a negative impact to Management students due to 1-2 hours of daily use for entertainment purposes. It was also found out that students who are obsessed to TikTok, aside from facing less concentration on studies, are more prone to issues such as mental instability and depression (Kaur, 2020)

CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Based on the result from the independent t-test analysis, it was found out that there is no statistically significant difference between gender and TikTok consumption. Also, there was no significant difference observed between gender and level of engagement. These rejects the hypotheses tested for this study. Based on the results, it can be concluded that regardless of gender, both groups are equal in using the application and highly engaged in their online classes. Also, from the Pearson correlation coefficient analysis performed, the findings revealed that there is a significant relationship found between TikTok consumption and level of class engagement of BPeA students. Thus, rejecting the hypothesis tested for this study. Since most of the responses from the students focuses more on the smart use of the application, it can be concluded that the higher the level of TikTok consumption of students in a smart way, the level of engagement is also increasing. Lastly, after the Linear regression analysis, the result yielded that there is a positive significant relationship between TikTok consumption and level of engagement of BPeA students. In this regard, it can be concluded that TikTok has a positive effect to the level of class engagement of students.

The present study on the effect of TikTok consumption to students’ class engagement establishes that the smart consumption of TikTok application may positively increase the level of engagement of students towards their online classes. There are several limitations that this study has. First, this study only focuses on Bachelor of Performing Arts students and does not generalize the entire population of students at City College of Angeles. It is highly recommended to include other programs from the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences including from the Institute of Business and Management, and Institute of Computing Studies and Library Information Science to further determine if the results will able to support the findings of this study or not. Second, the result of this study may not be applicable in another higher education institution. Hence, future researchers may find interest to conduct in-depth studies by comparing the results among different higher education institutions. Also, this study may be expanded to primary and secondary educational institutions since TikTok has been widely used by various ages. Future researchers

Table 11: Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypotheses	Result	Interpretation
H1 There is no significant difference between gender and TikTok consumption	Not Significant	Supported
H2 There is no significant difference between gender and level of class engagement.	Not Significant	Supported
H3 There is no significant relationship between TikTok consumption and level of class engagement.	Significant	Rejected
H4 TikTok consumption does not predict the level of class engagement of BPeA students.	Significant	Rejected

*TC-TikTok Consumption; CE-Class Engagement

may also be curious in adding moderating or mediating variables on the relationship of TikTok consumption and engagement to further determine the relationship between the two variables.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings revealed in this study, the following are the recommendations:

1. Based on the findings of this study, it was found that students are highly using TikTok application positively as a form of entertainment and recreation. Even the results turned on a positive note and as a helpful tool, previous conducted studies also revealed its negative effect to students. In this, the institute shall work hand-in-hand with the College Guidance and Formation Office (CGFO) in providing important information about the positive and negative effect (e.g., such as excessive consumption) of using TikTok application through seminars/webinars.

2. Numerous studies were conducted about the possible use of TikTok application as an educational tool. In this, instructors and professors may also use this application as another tool to provide a better and more engaging classroom environment. It can be used to disseminate important information about a topic and to showcase students' talents and understanding of the topic through short video clips.

3. Since students were seen as highly engaged in their online classes. Teachers should sustain this level by reserving more time for collaborative active learning. In this, students should have more time for collaborative active learning with their peers. Students do not need to have everything explained to them upfront – in fact, students learn more when they are given the autonomy to make academic discoveries on their own.

4. Students can become active and highly engaged in their own learning if they have structures for autonomy. In the traditional classroom setting, when students are working independently, the instructors' role is to support the students by checking students' work and provide coaching and feedback. In this current online class setting, teachers should gradually empower students to self-track their progress, coach their co-classmates, and turn to each other and their resources to seek for an answer to their questions. Students quickly become adept at personalizing the learning to one another's need.

5. Students should understand what they are expected to learn and achieve. In connection to this, teachers should provide learning targets, by breaking them into different sections so that students may be able to understand what they are expected to perform by the end of the lesson. Targets should be provided with success criteria so that students can self-assess and also track their own learning progress. This creates a structure where students can take ownership on their learning progress.

6. Monitor students' level of engagement and make adjustments if necessary. The most effective way to monitor engagement is to involve students in the process by having them use the learning targets and success

criteria provided to them. These keep students to be focused and provide you a concrete way of measuring whether students are engaged in their learning.

Acknowledgements

This study may not be possible without the support of the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences (IEAS) and the Office of the Vice President for Research, Extension and Quality Assurance (VPREQA) of City College of Angeles (CCA), the Institute of Arts, Sciences and Teacher Education (IASTE) of Mabalacat City College (MCC) and the Physical Education, Recreation and Sports (PERS) Department of Pampanga State Agricultural University (PSAU). Sincerest gratitude as well to all students who have participated in this study.

REFERENCES

- Baloran, E. T., Hernan, J. T., & Taoy, J. S. (2021). Course Satisfaction And Student Engagement In Online Learning Amid Covid-19 Pandemic: A Structural Equation Model. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 22(4), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.1002721>
- Gerald, B. (2018). A Brief Review of Independent, Dependent and One Sample t-test. *International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Theoretical Physics*, 4(2), 50. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijamtp.20180402.13>
- Hartono, F. P., Sumarno, N. U., & Puji, R. P. N. (2019). The level of student engagement based on gender and grade on history subject of senior high school students in jember regency. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(8), 21–26.
- Hayes, C., Stott, K., Lamb, K. J., & Hurst, G. A. (2020). "Making Every Second Count": Utilizing TikTok and Systems Thinking to Facilitate Scientific Public Engagement and Contextualization of Chemistry at Home. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(10), 3858–3866. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.0c00511>
- Jayarathne, D. N. (n.d.). *The Factors influencing for the tik tok application usage among youngsters during the epidemic period in Sri Lanka*. Retrieved May 29, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/66904721/The_Factors_influencing_for_the_tik_tok_application_usage_among_youngsters_during_the_epidemic_period_in_Sri_Lanka
- Kaur, P. (2020). Tik-Tok : Influence on Youth in India. *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(6), 4194–4207. <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/download/1658/1658/3210>
- Korlat, S., Kollmayer, M., Holzer, J., Lüftenegger, M., Pelikan, E. R., Schober, B., & Spiel, C. (2021). Gender Differences in Digital Learning During COVID-19: Competence Beliefs, Intrinsic Value, Learning Engagement, and Perceived Teacher Support. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12(March 2020), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.637776>
- Kraemer, H. C., & Blasey, C. (2016). Linear Regression Analysis. In *How Many Subjects?: Statistical Power Analysis in Research* (pp. 73–85). SAGE Publications,

- Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483398761.n6>
- Mekler, A. (2021). The Effects of TikTok Use on College Student Learning. *Undergraduate Review*, 16, 19. https://vc.bridgew.edu/undergrad_rev/vol16/iss1/19
- Montag, C., Yang, H., & Elhai, J. D. (2021). On the Psychology of TikTok Use: A First Glimpse From Empirical Findings. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9(March), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.641673>
- Nepali, S. (2021). The Social Media Impacts on Student's Education. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 7(5), 317–321. https://ijariie.com/AdminUploadPdf/The_Social_Media_Impacts_on_Student's_Education_ijariie15320.pdf
- Nugroho, I. S., Kusumawati, E., & Wahyuningsih, D. D. (2021). Student engagement during pandemic COVID-19 and its implications for guidance and counseling. *KONSELI : Jurnal Bimbingan Dan Konseling (E-Journal)*, 8(2), 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.24042/kons.v8i2.8778>
- Putu, N., Oktarini, U., Putu, N., Dewi, K., Riski, M., Kencana, A., & Arnas, J. H. (2022). *Analysis of the Positive and Negative Impacts of Using Tiktok For Generation Z During Pandemic*. 1(2).
- Salasac, C., & Lobo, J. (2022). The Rise Of Tiktok During Pandemic: Connection Of Tiktok To Students 'Engagement. *Universe International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 2(12), 19–26. <https://www.doi-ds.org/doi/10.2022-93352616/UIJIR>
- Schober, P., & Schwarte, L. A. (2018). Correlation coefficients: Appropriate use and interpretation. *Anesthesia and Analgesia*, 126(5), 1763–1768. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000002864>
- Sileyew, K. J.(2019). Research Design and Methodology. *Cyberspace*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/INTECHOPEN.85731>
- Vhatkar, A., & Mali, N. (2021). An Empirical analysis of use of TikTok by Management students in Pune city. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(2).https://www.cibgp.com/article_10254_fbc0872b1a3b5b895d07ccdcfa8731a6.pdf